

A THREE-DIMENSIONAL MICROMECHANICAL MODEL FOR NONLINEAR BEHAVIOR OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A nonlinear three-dimensional micromechanics approach for fibrous composites has been developed which is based on the relaxation of the coupling effect between the normal and shear stresses. The model lends itself very well to the inclusion of nonlinear behavior while maintaining a full three-dimensional capability. By incorporating the assumptions, a set of micromechanics equations are developed to predict mechanical properties, thermal properties, and constituent microstresses for the unidirectional fiber reinforced ply. Further, a thermoelastic-plastic analysis employing the Prandtl-Reuss flow relations with a strain hardening parameter and both isotropic and kinematic hardening was incorporated in the formulation. Results from the present analysis are compared with their counterparts from other models and experiment.

Keywords: composite micromechanics, microstresses, elastoplasticity, constitutive equations, fiber composites, mechanical properties

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years there has been a renewed interest in micromechanics techniques. Many methods have long existed for predicting composite material behavior when the material remains approximately linear such as the rule of mixtures which may be found in most elementary composite material textbooks [1] or the self-consistent methods [2]. However, due to the thrust for high temperature composite material applications, reliable predictions of composite behavior is desired in regimes where the material is highly nonlinear. Also, in many instances the materials of choice are metal-matrix composites whose constituents behave in the classical elastic-plastic manner. Therefore, new techniques for predicting composite behavior that can handle these difficulties are being developed.

One of the earliest of these newer methods is the vanishing fiber diameter model proposed by Bahei-El-Din [3]. This method assumes that the fibers possess a vanishingly small diameter even though they occupy a finite volume fraction of the composite. Therefore, only the longitudinal constraint between fiber and matrix is considered.

Hopkins and Chamis [4] proposed a model that analyzes the composite based on the response of a single representative volume element (RVE). Nonlinear thermoviscoplastic behavior is approximated through the use of power law relations where the ratio of the property of interest to a given reference value is set equal to a product of terms with unknown exponents [5].

The method that has been proposed by Aboudi [6] is more complex than these previous two models and represents a first order application of a higher order continuum theory earlier developed [7]. In this model, the RVE is divided into sub-cells and the displacement in each subcell is assumed to be linear. Continuity and equilibrium are then satisfied on an average basis between subcells and neighboring cells. This model offers a close approximation to the finite element method while reducing the total degrees of freedom that an equivalent finite element solution would require.

The present model [8] achieves a formulation similar to the Aboudi model but with the additional assumption that normal stresses applied to a unidirectional ply will not produce any shear stresses in either the fiber or matrix. All remaining continuity and equilibrium equations are satisfied so as to prevent any overlap or gaps in the material. Such a formulation further reduces the coupled degrees of freedom from that of the Aboudi model. Also, in the present formulation the matrix material is assumed to behave in the classical thermoelastic-plastic manner defined by a yield stress and strain hardening parameter while the fiber is assumed to be thermoelastic.

2. CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

Central to the present formulation is the assumption of a regular rectangular array of fibers distributed evenly in the matrix. A single RVE is analyzed by further assuming that symmetry applies and only one-quarter of the RVE is required for the mathematical formulation. The fiber and matrix are divided into various regions which consist of a set of rectangular parallelepiped matrix regions and a single prismatic fiber region whose edges are aligned with the coordinate axes. Additionally, in the formulation of the equilibrium and continuity conditions between the regions the shear stresses are forced to decouple from the normal stresses. Both four and eight region models have been analyzed and are pictorially represented in Figure 1.

A constant stress and strain state is assumed to exist within each region. The strain state within each region may be represented by

$$\{\epsilon\}_r = \{\epsilon\}_r^e + \{\epsilon\}_r^{th} + \{\epsilon\}_r^p \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is the engineering strain, the superscripts e, th, and p denote the elastic, thermal, and plastic strain components, and the subscript r denotes the region of interest.

From the stress-strain and thermal expansion relationships the strain may be related to the stress and temperature by

$$\{\epsilon\}_r = [S]_r \{\sigma\}_r + \{\alpha\}_r \Delta T + \{\epsilon\}_r^p \quad (2)$$

where [S] represents the constituent compliance matrix, σ the engineering stress, α the secant coefficient of thermal expansion, and ΔT the change in temperature from the reference value.

The continuity conditions require that the edges of the analysis cell remain plane during any normal applied stress. Also, inside the analysis cell no overlap or gaps may occur between the regions. The longitudinal constraint of the fiber ensures that all normal strains in the direction of the fiber are equal, and hence, the normal strain, ϵ_{11} , for each region is equal to the composite strain, ϵ_{11} . In addition, equilibrium is achieved between adjacent regions as well as with the applied composite stress through any cross-section of the RVE.

The continuity and equilibrium equations for the shear stresses, τ_{12} and τ_{13} , decouple due to the region configurations and may be solved separately. In accordance with the assumption it is desired that all shear stresses decouple from

Figure 1. Analysis Cell and Sample Region Configurations

the normal stresses. Therefore, in order to decouple the remaining shear stress, τ_{23} for each region is set equal to the applied composite stress, τ_{23} . With these conditions the equations may be simplified where for the four region model case all but six of the region stresses may be easily decoupled, and hence, the composite response may be described by

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ 6 \times 6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11f} \\ \sigma_{22f} \\ \sigma_{33f} \\ \sigma_{11m1} \\ \sigma_{33m1} \\ \sigma_{11m2} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} P_{Plast} \\ 6 \times 9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\epsilon\}_{m1}^P \\ \{\epsilon\}_{m2}^P \\ \{\epsilon\}_{m3}^P \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} (\alpha_{1m} - \alpha_{1f}) \Delta T \\ a(\alpha_{2m} - \alpha_{2f}) \Delta T \\ a(\alpha_{3m} - \alpha_{3f}) \Delta T \\ \bar{\sigma}_{11} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{22} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{33} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the overbar denotes composite stress, and the components of the $[P]$ and $[P_{Plast}]$ matrices as well as the equations that relate the remaining region stresses to those above are listed in reference [8]. Also, in the above equation the quantity $\{\epsilon\}^P$ for each subscripted matrix region represents the vector of normal plastic strains and may be defined for each region, r , using the Prandtl-Reuss flow relations by

$$\{\epsilon\}_r^p = \{\epsilon\}_{o_r}^p + \{d\epsilon\}_r^p = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{11}^p \\ \epsilon_{22}^p \\ \epsilon_{33}^p \end{pmatrix}_{o_r} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11}' \\ \sigma_{22}' \\ \sigma_{33}' \end{pmatrix}_r d\lambda_r \quad (4)$$

where the subscript, o, specifies the existing plastic strain before the given load increment, $d\lambda$ is an incremental plastic multiplier, and the prime specifies deviatoric stress.

The above equations along with the Von Mises yield condition are sufficient for solving the unidirectional composite thermoelastic-plastic response. Temperature dependent properties may also be included with minimal impact on the computational requirements.

3. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Both the four and eight region models required only modest computer resources for the cases discussed in this study (nonlinear results were obtained in a few seconds using a personal computer). However, since a potential use for the model is in thermomechanical fatigue cycling which would be much more computationally intensive, it would be beneficial to determine if the increased complexity of the eight region model provides any noticeable improvement in the results. Therefore, calculations from both the four and eight region models are presented in the majority of the figures.

Figures 2-4 present linear elastic results for graphite/epoxy at various fiber volume fractions. Calculations of composite elastic properties from the present formulation are compared to the Aboudi model and experimental data [6]. Constituent properties for the calculations were obtained from the reference [6]. The

Figure 2. Transverse Modulus for Graphite/Epoxy [6]

Figure 3. Transverse Poisson's Ratio for Graphite/Epoxy [6]

Figure 4. In-Plane Shear Modulus for Graphite Epoxy [6]

8-region model overpredicts both the transverse modulus, E_2 , and the in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , at the higher fiber volume fractions by approximately 10%. Also, the present formulation predicts an in-plane shear modulus that is on the order of 10% greater than that predicted by the Aboudi model, but the proposed model still demonstrates agreement with the experimental data. Overall, the models demonstrate excellent agreement with one another and experiment.

The nonlinear characteristics of the model under off-axis loading is depicted in Figure 5. The 0° , 10° , and 20° lamina predictions for Boron/Aluminum are presented for both the four and eight region models. The zero stress consolidation temperature for the composite was assumed to be 370°C , and the constituent properties used for the calculations are listed in reference [8]. The four and eight region model results are found to be indistinguishable from one another for the calculations shown in Figure 5. However, when the results for a 90° lamina are plotted as in Figure 6, it is found that yield occurs at an applied stress approximately 15% lower in the 8-region model case than that calculated by the 4-region model. Also, when the results are compared with experimental data [9], the 4-region model constructs a more reasonable estimate of the response. Therefore, for the cases examined in this study the more complex 8-region model offers no advantage over the simpler 4-region formulation and in some instances does not match experiments as closely as the 4-region model.

The model's effectiveness in capturing permanent strain during cyclic type loading has been demonstrated by Robertson and Mall [8] and compared with the experimental results of Kenaga, Doyle, and Sun [9]. An example of a 90° lamina Boron/Aluminum stress-strain response with periodic unloading after cooldown is presented in Figure 7. The 4-region micromechanics model presented in this paper was incorporated to estimate the experimental behavior. The results depict the model's capability for determining a unidirectional composite's behavior under thermomechanical loading.

Figure 5. Predicted Off-Axis Response for Boron / Aluminum 6061-T0

Figure 6. Predicted 90° Boron / Aluminum 6061-T0 Response [9]

Figure 7. 90° Boron/Aluminum Response With Periodic Unloading [8]

4. CONCLUSIONS

The basic principles of a micromechanics model has been introduced and comparisons made with other published data. The model assumes a rectangular array of fibers distributed in the matrix. Also, it is assumed that the matrix may be represented by a set of rectangular parallelepipeds and the fiber by a single prismatic region where each region possesses a constant stress and strain state. In addition, all shear stresses are forced to decouple from the normal stresses in the continuity and equilibrium equations. The fiber is assumed to behave thermoelastically while the matrix is assumed to be thermoelastic-plastic defined by a yield stress and strain hardening parameter.

Calculations with both four and eight region micromechanics models were performed, and it was found that the increased complexity of the eight region model offered no improvement over the four region model in characterizing the composite behavior for the cases considered. Indeed, for some instances, such as the transverse normal and in-plane shear modulus at high volume fractions and the nonlinear 90° lamina response, the eight region model is less desirable for accurately predicting the experimental values referred to in this study.

The model demonstrates promise for nonlinear thermomechanical fatigue loading. Also, the material property input consists of the thermoelastic properties of both the fiber and matrix and the yield stress and strain hardening parameter of the matrix which are parameters that are usually readily available or easily obtained.

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